

TEACHING ENGLISH VOCABULARY EFFECTIVELY AND EFFICIENTLY

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Annotation: This article analyses the vocabulary of a language and vocabulary teaching methods and techniques and studies some methods, such as, Using demonstrations and showing pictures, teaching words in the context, reading the word and etc.

Key words: method, skill, vocabulary, technique, words, reading, listening, speaking

Changes are quick and inevitable. The need to teach in general and teach to English language effectively in particular is the challenge before all the teachers in Uzbekistan. Today, it has become mandatory for the academicians to rethink and revamp their teaching strategies with the changing times. Since there has been a constant change in the teaching methods and techniques all over the world in every subject, vocabulary teaching methods and techniques need desirable and radical changes in a view of the demanding job market in the globalized world. Vocabulary of a language is just like bricks of a high building. Despite quite small pieces, they are vital to the great structure. Wilkins rightly says, “Without grammar very little can be conveyed. but without vocabulary nothing can be conveyed”. Therefore the study of vocabulary is at the center while learning a new language. English being a second language or foreign language, one needs to learn vocabulary in the systematic way. If we want to use language effectively, we must have good stock of vocabulary. We cannot use the language, if we don’t know the words of that language. English language has vast vocabulary. It is the richest language of the world. One cannot learn a language without learning vocabulary. Therefore, the study of vocabulary has occupied the central place in teaching learning activities. Thornbury opines: “If you spend most of your time studying grammar, your English will not improve very much. You will see most improvement, if you learn more words and expressions. You can say very little with grammar, but you can say almost anything with words.” This speaks volumes about the significance of vocabulary in learning, developing and enriching English. Vocabulary is a very important means to express our thoughts and feeling, either in spoken or written form. Indeed, neither literature nor language exists without vocabulary. Famous imperialist poet, Rudyard Kipling says that words are the most powerful drug used by mankind. English being a second language or foreign

language, one needs to learn vocabulary in the systematic way. In fact, without vocabulary communication in a second or foreign language is not possible in a meaningful way. Vocabulary is needed for expressing meaning and in using the receptive (listening and reading) and the productive (speaking and writing) skills. It should be considered as an internal part of learning a foreign language since it leads the way to communication. Teaching vocabulary well is a key aspect of developing engaged and successful readers. “There is a great divide between what we know about vocabulary instruction and what we (often, still) do”. Traditional vocabulary instruction for many teachers involves having students look words up in the dictionary, write definitions, and use words in sentences. Using demonstrations and showing pictures Teacher can perform some words. It can be fun and frolic. It makes the class student-centered. Teacher can act and learners try to imitate it. For example, the words like jump, smile, cry, nap, sleep, and dance can be demonstrated. Miming works well with younger students. You can mime out emotions and everyday activities to teach new words. This method can be practiced at ease. It can win the favour of the students as learners like dramatizations and can easily learn through them. Many situations can be dramatized or demonstrated. This works well with young students or students studying a foreign language to help introduce them to new concepts. After explaining new vocabulary, you can then ask the students to perform the actions. Charts, pictures and maps can be used to develop students’ understanding of a particular concept or word. There are some good picture dictionaries available in the market. Teacher should make use of such dictionaries. For instance, using a picture of a ‘fish’, words related to the fish, such as gills, eyes, backbone, cold-blooded, water, big, small etc. can be taught. Some words work well with pictures, particularly nouns. This can also be a good way to introduce blocks of related words, which is often utilized in foreign language classes, such as nouns and verbs related to the classroom or the house. Pictures can also be used in printable worksheets and flashcards, where pictures are matched to the word they represent. Teaching words in the context Most people agree that vocabulary ought to be taught in context. Words taught in isolation are generally not retained. In addition, in order to grasp the full meaning of a word or phrase, students must be aware of the linguistic environment in which the word or phrase appears. Setting a good context which is interesting, plausible, vivid and has relevance to the lives of the learners, is an essential prerequisite for vocabulary teaching as it helps in both engaging the attention of the learners and naturally generating the target vocabulary. Reading the word Reading words aloud is also very beneficial. It makes a learner familiar with the word and also improves pronunciations of the learners. Sound can be an easy way to illustrate words that 387 describe sounds, such as whistle, scratching, and tinkling. You can make the sounds yourself, or bring in tapes or CDs for students to listen to and write down the

words that they hear. The situation can be made easy and interesting, if the teacher of English selects the vocabulary, grades the vocabulary and uses different techniques in the classroom. Teachers should focus on vocabulary, as it is the most essential aspect in any language and means of communication. We cannot express our feelings without words. Wallace states, ‘Not being able to find the word you need to express yourself is the most frustrating experience in speaking another language’.

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